

Elements of Secure Processing Environments

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Workshop Report V1.0

Authors: Irene Schlünder, Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, Erdina Ene

Reviewers: Juan González-García, Kaisa Silander, Heikki Lanu, Gard Thomassen, Luděk Matyska, Laia Codó, Morris Swertz, Lionel Grondin, Nils Hoffmann, Dalibor Kačmář, Heikki Lehväslaiho, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, Petr Holub

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Executive Summary of Workshop Outcomes

The objective of this workshop was to discuss elements of Secure Processing Environments (SPEs). It brought together experts from academia, industry, and policy makers to exchange on the basic technical and organisational requirements, best practices, and their relevance for the realisation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and in connection with recent developments within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Following presentations on OpenVRE and SecureVRE (Spain), Sensitive Cloud (Czech Republic), TSD (Norway), Molgenis (The Netherlands), Health Data Hub (France), de.NBI cloud (Germany), THL and Findata (both Finland), speakers agreed that many elements are indeed in place, according to these best practices. A regulatory roadmap, however, is needed and shall allow to retain a plurality of SPE providers. SPEs are meant to pave new ways, rather than closing doors, and thus require incorporating user needs, especially a ‘cultural change’ in service provision and corresponding training of staff. To keep pushing for a common view, SPEs should start building from different agreements on common technical elements that can ensure interoperability. This includes a basic agreement on Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), and even more so an agreement on where those operability points are to enable global collaboration.

This workshop was jointly organised by the EU-Projects EOSC-Life and HealthyCloud on 19-20th of June 2023 in Brussels/online. It attracted more than 150 participants.

Acronyms

BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular resources Research Infrastructure (Austria)
BMS RI	Biomedical Science Research Infrastructure
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Spain)
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
CSC	IT Center for Science (Finland)
de.NBI	German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure
DGA	Data Governance Act
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
Findata	Social and Health Data Permit Authority (Finland)
IACS	Health Sciences Institute in Aragon (Spain)
MUNI	Masaryk University (Czech Republic)
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (Finland)
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
TSD	Service for Sensitive Data (Norway)
UMCG	University Medical Center Groningen (The Netherlands)

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Workshop on Elements of Secure Processing Environments

Purpose

HealthyCloud, B1MG, PHIRI, HRIC, EOSC-Life, EUCAIM etc are EU projects where BioMedical Science Research Infrastructures (BMS RIs) together with other consortium partners are tasked to provide input and recommendations to policy makers for shaping the future data landscape in the field of health research. In parallel, the EU Commission driven by DG Sante is building a European Health Data Space (EHDS) with numerous implications for research and realised with projects such as EHDS2-pilot.

Many projects and the European law such as the Data Governance Act (DGA) and the draft EHDS Regulation are built on the assumption that personal data should only be processed in a Secure Processing Environment (SPE) defined as *'the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to provide the opportunity to re-use data in a manner that allows for the operator of the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including to display, storage, download, export of the data and calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms'* in Art. 2 (14) DGA.

The workshop presented already existing SPEs as best practices and allowed to extract and discuss the basic technical and organisational requirements to build such an SPE in compliance with the DGA and the EHDS along the lines of the following questions:

- Is there consensus on technical and organisational measures on Secure Processing Environments (SPEs)? Nationally and/or internationally and/or domain-specific? (We already know internationally there is close to none now.)
- What certifications are used (also where) to demonstrate the compliance? Nationally and/or internationally and/or domain-specific?
- What are the approval mechanisms in different countries?

Audience

- Researchers (academia and industry)
- Research Infrastructure Representatives (national and EU)
- EU Commission Representatives from DG RTD
- EU Commission Representatives from DG Sante
- EU Commission Representatives from DG Justice
- EDPB Representative
- EDPS Representative
- DPA Representatives
- National Ministry Representatives
- Patient Organisations

Outline

Following the welcome note, an introduction on terminology around SPEs as well as a presentation of results from HealthyCloud and EOSC-Life by Irene Schlünder (TMF), Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI-ERIC) and Juan González-García (IACS) were followed by eight best practice examples:

1. Presentation: Kaisa Silander, THL (Finland) and Heikki Lanu, Findata (Finland)
2. Presentation: Gard Thomassen, TSD, (Norway)
3. Presentation: Luděk Matyska, MUNI, SensitiveCloud (Czech Republic)
4. Presentation: Laia Codó, BSC, OpenVRE vs SecureVRE (Spain)
5. Presentation: Morris Swertz, UMCG, Molgenis (The Netherlands)
6. Presentation: Lionel Grondin, Health Data Hub (France)
7. Presentation: Nils Hoffmann, de.NBI Cloud (Germany)
8. Presentation: Dalibor Kačmář, National Technology Officer, Microsoft (Czech Republic)

The concluding panel discussion comprising all speakers and Heikki Lehvälaiho (CSC) aimed to shed light on the following topics:

- Technical security (including the use of clouds)
- Organisational measures such as roles (e.g., controller, processor)
- Certification

Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (BSC) and Petr Holub (BBMRI-ERIC) closed the meeting with key outcomes.

Summary of Best Practice Examples

1. Kaisa Silander from the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) and Heikki Lanu from Findata gave a presentation on the workings of their institution's secure processing environment. Kaisa explained that their institution has many unique databases that were developed for other purposes but can be used by researchers for research purposes. If the researcher receives a positive reply from THL Biobank about their request, they get a copy of the data coded with project-specific identifiers (not the original data). The researcher can then use it in their own secure environment, but all results should be returned to the biobank. So far, this is the only operating model they have in place, but they are looking for other models where the data does not get downloaded. They recommend their users to use the HUS Acamedic (provided by Helsinki University Hospital (HUS)) secure environment or the SD Desktop service from CSC. THL is collaborating with CSC in developing the SD services but that is still a work in progress.

Heikki explained that Finland passed the 2019 Secondary Use Act that established Findata and tasked it to create the requirement regulation for SPEs. The first version of this regulation was published in October 2020 and it was revised in January 2022. Starting from February 2022 there are currently nine registered SPEs.

2. Gard Thomassen presented the work of TSD, which was firstly built as a service for sensitive data, but then grew so popular that they needed to build a new one for all types of data. He

explained that TSD has a data portal where one can import or export data (if allowed to do so). The service can be used from everywhere, regardless of the researcher's location in the world. Nonetheless, the export is tightly controlled. From a technical view on SPE, they expressed that they must have APIs on everything. The APIs should be controlled, but they have to be there. From an organisational view, standardisation is great, but he explained that if they standardise everything, then it might hinder the speed of development. To sum it all up, they believe they shouldn't make it too complicated. Research and clinical use are not the same and they should hard code the technological requirements and have a reasonable amount of auditing.

3. Luděk Matyska presented E-INFRA CZ as the only national research e-infrastructure, which is a consortium of three originally independent organisations. He explained that they tried to create a specific environment for supporting highly sensitive data: the SensitiveCloud. The access to the cloud is enabled through VPNs only and the data is anonymised by them. In this way, no one will have access to the processing of data. This will be expanded in the next phase, while they are trying to build something that is useful and helpful to the public.

4. Laia Codó presented the secure processing environment at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. She explained that OpenVRE is what they use as an analysis platform, which they utilise for accessing and analysing data. The focus was to have a product that was portable, flexible, and scalable and the result was OpenVRE. How it works: When a researcher accesses the analysis platform, they can decide if they want to login or not. After that, they can choose different ways of importing data into the environment, from the user's devices or any associate data providers. In the end, the user has all the data under their control in this workspace and can operate the data through a set of predefined tools, which are defined per OpenVRE instance. After that, the user can either fit these results into another tool or visualise it. There is also the authentication/authorisation server. At BSC, they have several ways of processing the jobs depending on the use case of the specific project: They can delegate executions to HPC systems, to local virtual clusters, and to remote clouds. At the end, they have a tool (or pipeline) that has been encapsulated inside a container with an adaptor acting as entry-point and limited access to

user or project specific data volumes. They believe that OpenVRE incorporates all the technical elements to become a trusted environment, and it is time to start defining their governance plan to put in place this secure environment, which is code-named 'SecureVRE'.

5. Morris Swertz explained the workings of the secure processing environment at the University Medical Center in Groningen. They work with three different studies. One of them is multi-centered cohort studies, where a lot of data has been collected in rich databases in Europe and the key is to be able to analyse those, while first making them comparable. Another one is enough rare diseases data. This one is not concerned with having a lot of data sets, but instead finding enough rare data and being able to jointly analyse it. The last category is data that is collected for reasons other than research, which they are trying to harmonise and integrate. When it comes to the data federation, they operate two of them. One is the distributed version (where the data stays at the source) and the other is the centralised version (where people are willing to share some of the data to a central place). They have built the federated SPE using DataShield. The way it works is that they have a central analysis computer where one can write scripts using R (the statistics language) and then DataShield sends all these analyses to each of the participating data holders. The analysis is executed inside but it is called Data Shield because it does not allow any sensitive data to leak out. What is special about Data Shield is that one does not need to first create a complete analysis and then package that but instead every and each command is being shielded. This is then distributed and each of the participating nodes executes it locally on the data.

6. Lionel Grondin presented the secure processing environment of Health Data Hub. He explained that the Health Data Hub is the only French cloud technology platform and how it allows health data projects to have access to elastic capacities. He described it as a technological platform that provides a set of tools supporting research projects with a public interest to access, analyse, and process health data. He then proceeded to show how the remote access of the secure processing environment of the Health Data Hub works. Finally, the architecture and organisational principles of their security model was presented.

7. Nils Hoffman started by presenting a schematic overview of the de.NBI cloud and proceeded by showing the federated operational and IT security certification concept of it. The three elements that make up the secure research environment were showcased, and three use case examples were explained: First, the OTP2EOSC – Research Appliance and OTP2EOSC – Research Environment, which implement GA4GH standards, specifically for execution of hybrid workflows, and integrate them into a secure cloud environment. He then presented the BIH - Charite - Clinical Cloud, which, based on local data protection requirements, represents an on-premise research cloud with highly restrictive access. The Clinical Cloud as a platform is a part of the Health-X dataspace in the domain Health of the Gaia-X ecosystem, which allows researchers and companies to access and use (pseudonymised and summarised) patient data in a controlled way.

8. Dalibor Kačmář from Microsoft (Czech Republic) held a presentation about confidential computing, specifically Azure's Confidential Computing. The presentation proceeded with an explanation of the Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) to minimise attack surface to CPU, and app enclave as an example of TEE. Then, the five elements of TEE foundations were presented: hardware root-of-trust, remote attestation, trusted launch, memory isolation and encryption, secure key management. He explained the principles of Confidential Computing in Azure and showed that Azure has multiple levels to support confidential computing: attestation, confidential keys, and confidential 1P services. He then proceeded to present the full VM-level protection.

Reflections from the Panel Discussion

For Researchers

- SPEs exist to make data available for research that would otherwise not be accessible.
- SPEs are not the only conceivable means to share data for research and the established gateways should remain.
- Standardisation and the development of SOPs is needed as well as well-defined building blocks and a common understanding how the whole building will look like.
- A clear language and proper terminology are needed, as well as an understanding of the different levels and roles.
- Constant alignment and collaboration should ensure that we resolve problems, rather than creating new ones.
- SPEs can offer many opportunities and services, but training is needed to make them usable.

For Policy Makers

- There is still a need to reduce complexity and build trust through standardisation and certification.
- There is no one-fits-all solution, since research needs flexibility and technology changes quickly, so that constant updating is necessary.
- Bottom-up approaches seem to be more promising than top down, since development needs to be user driven.
- The community needs more funding for Coordination and Support Action (CSA) projects to drive interoperability and Code of Conduct initiatives and the development of SOPs.
- Funding for training programs is needed.

For Citizens

- SPEs are a powerful means to balance citizens' interests in privacy on the one hand and research progress on the other hand.
- SPEs can foster transparency through providing access for citizens to their own data.
- Citizens should play an important role in the data sharing governance around the use of SPEs.

Key Outcomes

The workshop concludes that **a roadmap for SPEs is required and should, most critically, allow for a plurality of SPE providers** that, in return, share common building blocks to ensure interoperability. For this to materialise, SPEs need to agree on what those interoperability points are (e.g., standard operating procedures (SOPs)). **Likewise, a change in culture is indispensable.** SPE providers have to offer their services to users and move away from the understanding that users need to be protected of themselves. Rather, the requirements and experiences of users must be considered and optimised. **In response, SPEs have the potential of becoming spaces for innovation, opening new ways of scientific collaboration for the benefit of society.**

To achieve this goal, **it is critical to balance secure processing with accessibility and user needs.** This requires a good understanding of what it means to establish and operate a SPE on the one hand and for whom and what specific purpose in sensitive data handling services and solutions should be provided on the other hand. Technology - of course - is and always will be a moving target, as are risks and opportunities. **To tackle these challenges and opportunities, researchers, policy makers and the citizens thus need to continue the conversation** and hold workshops such as this on a regular basis taking the provider and user viewpoints into account.

